

Evaluating Clinical Judgement Items: Field Test Results

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Research Questions

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2. Are Clinical Judgment and Nursing Knowledge separate dimensions?

Data Collection: Assembling Items and Forms – JUL17

- 110 Clinical Judgement items developed based on panel methodology
- Items assembled into 11 non-overlapping forms
- Each form had 20 items:
10 newly developed CJ items, 10 from the existing item bank

Equating Forms

- Forms built such that the NCLEX portion was equated on test characteristic curve for overall difficulty across the theta range (centered at 0.0 logits with a 1.0 SD)
- To distribute difficulty of CJ items across forms:
used previous data from usability studies and reading load
- The first two items across the forms were easy and the rest of the items were randomized

Filtering Candidates

Because this was an optional field test section, we wanted to include candidates who had shown a baseline effort in answering items, so we implemented following criteria for valid cases:

1. Answered all items on the field test section
2. Spent at least 15 minutes on the entire field test section
(10 NCLEX * 30 seconds + 10 CJ * 60 seconds = 15 minutes)

Completers

- 56,750 examinees participated in field test
- 30,108 were considered completers (53%)
- Completers vs. non-completers were similar in terms of passing rates (78% vs 71%)
- Results were replicated in a later quarter

1. What are the optimal scoring rules for each item type?

1. Plus/Minus

2. 0/1

3. Rationale

Plus/Minus Scoring

- Over/under responding is allowed
- Total score = sum of response scores
- If Total < 0, then Total = 0

Example Item: Plus/Minus Scoring

➤ Which of the following actions should the nurse take?
Select all that apply.

- Check the client's pupils for equality of size +1
- Check the client's weight and compare to prior findings.
- Check the client's skin turgor. +1
- Request a prescription to administer additional water via the feeding tube.
- Request a prescription to obtain a stool culture. -1
- Request a change from enteral nutrition to parenteral nutrition. —

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0/1 Scoring

- When only specific # of responses allowed
- 1 if selection is correct, otherwise 0
- Total score = sum of response scores

Example Item: 0/1 Scoring

The client has a temperature of 102.1° F (38.9° C) at this time. The nurse notes that the fetal heart rate (FHR) is 170 with minimal variability and no accelerations present. Contractions are every 7 minutes, and last 50 seconds with moderate intensity. A category II fetal heart rate (FHR) tracing is noted.

➤ Drag words from the choices below to fill in each blank found in the following sentence:

The best outcomes for the client would be to []
and []. To achieve optimal outcomes, the nurse
should [] and [].

Word Choices

Reduce maternal temperature

Facilitate labor progression

Improve fetal well-being

Prepare for cesarean section

Perform intrauterine resuscitation

Administer intravenous antibiotics

Discontinue intravenous oxytocin

Rationale Scoring

- When item has 2 conditions that must be met, e.g. do this because of that
- 1 point for getting both responses correct, otherwise 0

Example Item: Rational Scoring

Which three medications would require clarification prior to administration? Complete the following sentences by choosing from the lists of options.

The nurse should not administer the because

1. What are the optimal scoring rules for each item type?

As the number of possible score categories increased, the potential for items to fit poorly increased

2. Are Clinical Judgment and Nursing Knowledge separate dimensions?

CFA models least to most complex:

1. Uni-dimensional all items scored independently (1-dim)
2. Uni-dimensional with polytomously scored scenarios (1dim-poly)
3. Two-dimensional all items scored independently (2-dim)
4. Bifactor with all CJ items as single group factor (Bifactor)
5. Bifactor with testlet structure on scenario items (Bi-testlet)

CFA fit statistics

- CFI \geq .90
- RMSEA $<$.05
- CFIT $>$.90
- SRMR $<$.08
- RMSEA $<$.06 + SRMR $<$.09
(Hu & Bentler, 1999)

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All forms had good model fit based on this criteria

CFA Results: Comparative Fit Index Values

	Forms										
Model	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1-dim	.87	.94	.78	.74	.94	.93	.82	.82	.82	.69	.94
1dim-poly	.91	.95	.78	.79	.94	.90	.87	.86	.80	.91	.94
2-dim	.89	.94	.78	.77	.94	.93	.83	.83	.82	.71	.94
Bifactor	.97	.94	.84	.89	.96	.97	.93	.88	.85	.95	.97
Bi-testlet	.97	.97	.82	.91	.95	.97	.95	.88	.92	.93	.97

CFA Results

1. Single dominant dimension is present across all items
2. The results of the 1dim-poly and Bi-testlet indicate that scenario items are dependent
3. 1dim-poly model is the most parsimonious model that fits the data well

Replication

- OCT17 – Single dimensional model fit all forms
- JAN18 – Replication of JUL17 forms with same results
- APR18 – Uni-dimensional was a good fit on 17 of 20 forms
- Overall: uni-dimensional model with independently scored items has good fit with incrementally better fit on only the CFI across forms with the use of super-poly or bifactor

Summary: What are the optimal scoring rules for each item type?

- Recommended Scoring Methods:
 - Plus/Minus scoring when over- or under-responding is allowed.
 - 0/1 scoring when a fixed number of selections are available.
 - Rationale scoring: options must be tightly coupled for correctness.
- As the number of options increases, the item misfit increases.

Summary: Are Clinical Judgment and Nursing Knowledge separate dimensions?

- A single, dominant dimension was found underlying the data.
- A uni-dimensional model with polytomous scoring of both items and scenarios provided good fit.
- Scoring scenarios as a collection of items showed a superior fit when compared to the single dimensional model.